

Defense Diplomacy Strategy in Global Governance to Face the Global Threats

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ABSTRACT: Global developments that are full of dynamics are marked by the emergence of interdependence between countries. Global developments are in line with the development of science and technology which causes countries to seem borderless. The blurring of boundaries between countries and the development of an increasingly dynamic environment are also accompanied by the development of increasingly broad and multidimensional threats. This global development is also marked by the emergence of new actors in international relations. The development of threats and increasing global issues that cannot be handled by the state alone have created a new phenomenon in the international relations order, namely global governance. Previously, the state was the sole actor in the order of international relations. However, with global governance, there is a new arrangement in the international relations system that accommodates all actors who play a role. This research will use a qualitative phenomenological method. The theory used in this research are global governance, defense diplomacy and international organization as a basis theory and concept, and also a security theory as supporting theory. In the end, we can see that the change of international order can bring the positive effect for countries in achieving their national goals and accomplish their national interests.

KEYWORDS: Global Governance, International Relation, Defense Diplomacy, Global Threats, Covid-19

INTRODUCTION

In the current era of globalization, many things continue to change from time to time. The strategic environment, both national, regional and even global, continues to change and tends to be dynamic. The dynamics that exist make the world and global governance increasingly complex. The existing threats are increasingly varied, ranging from military threats, non-military threats to hybrid threats. The phenomenon of globalization and its various aspects seems to be breaking down traditional boundaries between countries and erasing physical distances between countries. The development of technology, communication, and weapons shows how national borders are becoming less relevant in international relations in this era of globalization. The global threat that is a common enemy is currently rife, namely the Covid-19 pandemic. This pandemic has become very important after almost all countries in the world have experienced this pandemic. Thousands of people have died due to the Covid-19 virus. The economies of countries in the world are in free fall, causing many countries to experience an economic recession. Countries are attacking each other and accusing each other about who first caused this Covid-19 pandemic. Not only that, the problem of the Covid-19 pandemic is coupled with other problems that are no less complicated. Defense diplomacy in this case tries to play a role in global governance to find solutions to the problems and threats that occur today. We will also see how the governance relationship of international relations was before and after the Global Governance phenomenon, as well as the position of the international regime in this global governance.

The emergence of a deeper pattern of interdependence and the emergence of global similarities is an important call for increased and more effective forms of international collective action (Papaconstantinou & PisaniFerry, 2019). The concept of security has undergone many changes. The current concept of security is interdependence in all global problems (UNESCO, 1995). Global governance is the governance of relations in today's international world. A state-centered approach to world politics has become difficult to maintain and it is no longer possible to treat the state as the only important actor on the international stage (Heywood, 2011). Currently, the roles of non-state actors such as IGOs, NGOs, multi-national corporations, and also experts are increasing. Global governance underscores the governance that is carried out between countries such as institutionalization, the formation of global rules and the formulation of increasingly complex rules (Hurrell, 2007).

The study of international relations experienced rapid development, especially in continental Europe during the Westphalian Treaty of 1648. Until 1900, relations between countries became a social science study. The study of international relations is a finding of Western culture and was initially more concerned with the interests of major powers involved in the arena of war and international peace (Hadiwinata, 2017). The development of the study of international relations is very dynamic along with the times.

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THEORY AND CONCEPT

This research will use global governance, defense diplomacy and international organization as a basis theory and concept, and also a security theory as supporting theory. Global governance is the governance of relations in today's international world. The term global governance was first introduced by James N. Rosenau and Ernst-Otto Czempiel in a book entitled *Governance without Government Order and Change in World Politics*. In the book Rosenau argues can there be a profound transformation in the nature of global governance without a change in citizen skills and orientation? The judgment stems from the assumption that while much research on the dynamics of global governance and order remains to be done, it is not too early to speculate on the implications of its investigations on future world politics (Rosenau, 1992). These efforts are based on a theoretical understanding rather than a factual understanding of the transformations currently at work in world politics. This concept is based on the assumption that globalization has led to a traditional political crisis, and the demand for mechanisms or functions equivalent to governance is enormous. How does governance relate to government? Although clearly related, they are not identical. Rosenau's statement was also reinforced by Lawrence Finkelstein who said that "*global governance is governing without sovereign authority*" (Finkelstein, 1995, pp. 367-372). In the process of its development, the concept of global governance is considered as a way to replace the role of international regulations that cannot be fulfilled or played by a country. Thus, it can be said that global governance can replace the role of a country in dealing with global issues.

This research will use a qualitative phenomenological method. The researcher explains in detail the problems that are being faced related to the existing phenomena in detail and the efforts to solve them. In an effort to complete this research, the researcher tries to discuss the efforts made from the perspective of defense diplomacy by looking at the global governance phenomenon that exists in life in today's world. With the hope that the handling of the problems that exist in today's global, can be handled accurately and of value. In this case, data collection is done by means of a literature study.

INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

If we talk about global governance, it's certainly not complete if we don't talk about international organizations. Parts of global governance are cooperative problem-solving arrangements and activities undertaken by states and other actors to deal with various problems and issues at hand. They include international or transnational structures such as formal international intergovernmental organizations (IGOs) and international non-governmental organizations (NGOs/NGOs), international rules or laws, norms, and international regimes in which rules, norms and structures are linked together in a problem area. certain, ad hoc arrangements and global conferences, and private and hybrid or mixed public and private governance schemes. An IGO is an organization that includes at least three states among its membership, which has activities in several states, and that is created through formal intergovernmental agreements such as treaties, charters, or laws. These IGOs can be distinguished based on the scale of their coverage areas, namely subregional, regional and global. IGOs can also be distinguished based on their objectives, general and specific. An example of a well-known global scale IGO is the UN or the United Nations, in Indonesia itself the UN is known as the United Nations. In regional scope, IGOs that are well known are ASEAN (Association of South East Asian Nation), whose members are countries in Southeast Asia or the European Union (European Union) whose members consist of 27 countries on the European continent. Then, IGOs are differentiated based on their goals, general and specific. Examples of IGOs with general purposes such as OAS (Organization of America States), then examples of IGOs with specific objectives such as WHO (World Health Organization), WTO (World Trade Organization) where both IGOs are under the supervision of the UN or UN. The function of the IGO itself is as a means to exchange information between its member countries, as a forum for exchanging opinions, as a rule maker to overseeing regulations for its member countries. As Karns put it, "*IGOs do not only create opportunities for their member states, but also exercise influence and impose constraints on their member states' policies and processes*" (Karns & Mingst, 2010)

Furthermore, in the book written by Karns and Mingst, "*NGOs are private voluntary organizations whose members are individuals or associations that come together to achieve a common purpose*" (Karns & Mingst, 2010). Some of these organizations or NGOs are formed to support specific goals, such as human rights, peace, or environmental protection. Others were established to provide services such as disaster relief, humanitarian assistance or development assistance in war-torn communities. Examples of well-known NGOs are Medecins Sans Frontieres (Doctors Without Borders), the World Wildlife Fund (WWF), Human Rights Watch, and others.

This International Organization was formed based on a combination of several factors. Andrew Heywood in his book entitled *Global Politics* says, "*International organizations are created out of a composite of factors. These include the existence of interdependencies among states which encourage policy-makers to believe that international cooperation can serve common interests, and the presence of a hegemonic power willing and able to bear the costs of creating, and sustaining, an international organization*" (Heywood, 2011). The interdependence factor among the countries in the world creates a belief that international cooperation is able to accommodate and serve common interests, which can be realized by the existence of international organizations.

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DEFENSE DIPLOMACY

Traditionally, the role of the armed forces has relied on a functional need to use or threaten to use force, whether for defence, deterrence, coercion, or intervention. The concept of defense diplomacy encapsulates these changes. In the book written by Andrew Cottey, *“Defense diplomacy, in contrast, involves the peacetime cooperative use of armed forces and related infrastructure (primarily defense ministries) as a tool of foreign and security policy”*. He also said that defense diplomacy includes various activities in it, such as military cooperation, military assistance, warship visits, or exchange of officers between countries. The use of defense diplomacy as a means of building trust and cooperation between former or potential enemies, so as to help prevent conflict. Defense diplomacy can contribute to conflict prevention in various ways, such as demonstrating political commitment to developing cooperative relations, increasing military transparency and reducing misunderstandings, increasing awareness of common interests, and promoting military cooperation (Cottey & Forster, 2004)

Defense diplomacy has become an important tool in foreign policy and national security. This is the result of three important developments. The first is the development of the nature of the challenges between countries that have developed, the two countries are increasingly accepting the need for multilateral diplomacy and institutional building to better defend and promote their national interests. And finally, the role of the military has evolved in the post-Cold War period. Today's military must diversify its core tasks from the traditional war focus to include new and diverse roles, such as peacekeeping, disaster relief, and greater participation in national defense diplomacy.

In a book entitled *From 'Boots' to 'Brogues'*, it is stated that, *“Defense diplomacy involves cooperation between militaries over a range of issues that include traditional duties of the military, such as counter-balancing efforts against rivals, and new roles that are outside of the traditional duties, such as peacekeeping, peace enforcement, promoting good governance, responding to natural and humanitarian disasters, protecting human rights and, at least in the Western context, supporting liberal democracy..... The significant consequence for defense diplomacy is that the military and its related infrastructure becomes a more engaged institution in the practice of diplomacy and foreign policymaking alongside other institutions that have traditionally dominated the foreign policymaking process”* (Singh & Tan, 2011)

Now, defense diplomacy is defined as all the methods and strategies used by countries that may be in competition with other countries, but they have used certain types of practices, including economics, culture, political cooperation, defense cooperation, and diplomacy to make friends, with the hope that they can work together, and the most important thing is to build and increase mutual trust (Pedrason, 2015)

Defense diplomacy or defense diplomacy is international cooperation in the defense sector which is an integral part of Indonesia's diplomacy based on Pancasila, the 1945 Constitution, legislation, policies and defense strategies as well as the results of studies on the strategic environment both globally and regionally (Simamora, 2013). Defense diplomacy is one of the efforts made by the state in achieving national interests.

National defense diplomacy is not only carried out through state defense practices, but also through economic, cultural, and political cooperation to build and increase mutual trust. Defense diplomacy has three main characteristics, namely defense diplomacy in the *confidence building measure*, *capacity building*, and *defense industry* (Anwar, Lasmono, & Nuzulia, 2017).

SECURITY THEORY

Security is most often associated with the alleviation of threats to cherished values: especially those that, if left unchecked, threaten the survival of certain referent objects in the near term (Williams, 2008). To be clear, although safety and survival are often associated, they are not the same. Whereas survival is a condition for survival, security involves the ability to pursue valuable political and social ambitions.

Therefore, it is best to understand security as a “survival plus” mentioned by Ken Booth (Booth, 2007). "Plus" means avoiding life-threatening threats, so there are many choices in life.

Published by Barry Buzan in 1983, the book entitled *People, States, and Fear* succeeded in encouraging many people to acknowledge the existence of components, especially non-military state security. He argued that a nation's military security was only one feature, and that states should pay attention to threats to their political system, economic resources, society, and environment. Although non-military insights emerged only during the 1980s, topics such as deterrence, nuclear and conventional military balance, and superpower power projection capabilities remained central (Buzan, 1983)

DEFENSE DIPLOMACY IN GLOBAL GOVERNANCE

The governance that exists in the international world today is different from the phenomenon of global governance or global governance. Significant differences occur in many emerging international organizations in the world today. In the past, countries thought that they had to work alone to achieve all their national interests. Cooperation with other countries has not been deemed necessary by many countries. However, as time goes by, globalization occurs in this world, increasingly blurring and unclear national boundaries, sometimes causing conflicts between adjacent countries. With things like this, it requires every person or country to interact with each other. The world community interacts with each other to realize all their interests, especially the interests of their

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countries. However, it is not uncommon for a country's national interests to clash with the interests of other countries. This in turn can lead to conflicts and global threats. To facilitate the achievement of the national interest of a country, the existing countries take the initiative to form international organizations. Countries through this organization will strive to achieve common interests, and these interests involve a very wide area of international life, because these fields involve the interests of many countries. This international organization also plays an important role in implementing, monitoring, and mediating in disputes that arise from decisions made by states (Viotti & Kauppi, 1993)

The current Covid-19 pandemic in Indonesia is a disease outbreak that also affects many countries in the world. This pandemic not only caused casualties, but also caused losses in various fields such as the economic and political fields. To solve the problem of the Covid-19 pandemic, countries can't just rely on what they have. Of course, countries in the world must help each other to overcome this corona virus outbreak. Coronavirus disease or Covid-19 was first infected in Wuhan City at the end of 2019. On January 30, 2020, the World Health Organization (WHO) declared Covid-19 as an emergency, and needed international treatment or Public Health Emergency of International Concern (PHEIC), and on March 11 it was first declared a pandemic. In these circumstances, it is time to show solidarity, act responsibly, and work together to achieve the common goal of ensuring food supply, food security and nutrition, and improving the overall well-being of people around the world.

International organizations are often blamed when global problems arise, or are criticized for violating state sovereignty in the name of global interests, or for failing to implement an agenda to achieve stated goals. No country can solve this problem alone, so international cooperation is the obligation of all governments to address global issues as they are today (Djelantik, 2020, pp. 113-120)

In terms of handling this pandemic, the international organization involved is WHO (World Health Organization). As explained above, WHO is one of the IGOs under the auspices of the United Nations or the United Nations. In addition to the WHO, international organizations that also play a role in handling the Covid-19 pandemic are the G20 or a group of 20 major economies, which are a group of 19 countries with the largest economies in the world plus the European Union. However, these two organizations are still considered ineffective, because the two organizations have not worked together effectively to deal with this global pandemic. Non-governmental organizations are still not widely involved in formulating concrete action policies. Equally important is the lack of international organizations and state governments to manage global media.

In addition to international organizations such as WHO, handling this pandemic also involves diplomatic cooperation in the defense sector, because the Covid-19 pandemic is also a non-military threat. Indonesia itself is involved in cooperation in the defense sector, including cooperation in handling the Covid-19 pandemic within the framework of the ASEAN Defense Ministers' Meeting (ADMM). Indonesia took part in the virtual ASEAN Defense Senior Officials' Meeting (ADSOM) on May 15, 2020. This conference is also a good opportunity to exchange views on the regional and international security situation in the context of the Covid-19 pandemic. Therefore, it is very important for ASEAN countries to make comprehensive efforts through the exchange of information, medical assistance, and expansion of cooperation in the field of soft policy and regulation (Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Indonesia, 2020). From this, it can be seen that global governance, including various international organizations, plays a very important role in dealing with global threats, which of course are common threats to all countries in the world.

CONCLUSION

From all the explanations that have been explained, it can be concluded that global governance has changed along with the development of the world's people's lives and also the strategic environment which is very dynamic and is VUCA. Global governance is a concept that describes the governance of relations in the international world today. In this case, international relations are not regulated by a single authority and there are roles of non-state actors even though the state still plays an important role in international relations. Global governance has norms, rules, and standards known as international regimes. Currently, there are many threats and issues that cannot be solved by the state alone, but are resolved together in a global order. All of these things also cause the threats that exist in the world to become increasingly complex and diverse. Threats are no longer only in the form of military threats such as attacks by armed forces from one country to another, but also non-military threats, such as the current disease outbreak. The handling of nonmilitary threats, of course, cannot be equated with military threats. The enemy in the non-military threat, the Covid-19 pandemic, is not something that can be faced with weapons or defense equipment. The enemy that exists is not real, namely the Covid-19 virus itself. The position of international organizations in this regard is included in global governance. International organizations help solve global problems, especially problems that occur in their member countries. In addition to international organizations, the role of diplomacy, especially defense diplomacy, is also important in handling this pandemic. Defense diplomacy can be directly involved in seeking information related to pandemic developments from other countries through defense attaches in many countries, as well as cooperation in the defense sector such as the ASEAN Defense Ministers' Meeting (ADMM). Cooperation in the defense sector like this is considered quite helpful to other international organizations, such as WHO.

Strengthening coordination between international organizations in the world is considered to be increased to deal with this pandemic so that it ends soon. In addition to the UN, WHO, G20 and other IGOs, non-governmental organizations or NGOs may be able to assist the existing IGOs and defense cooperation. Countries must also increase their trust in each other, and first get rid

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of all their respective egos for the realization of common interests. And also, internal problems between countries must also be set aside first, so that the handling of the Covid-19 pandemic can be maximized. Lastly, let's take care of each other together to make the world as it used to be, or maybe even better.

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